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Primary Education in Developing Countries and Teacher's Educational Role, Training and Development

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Abstract:

The purpose of this essay is to explore and understand a meaningful module of primary education that can be prosperous for the entire human being worldwide. The analysis of its pros and cons, which has been discussed here and thus, has tried to focus on a true module of education, and its modern attitude that can be set up on the base of gender and community's equality, equity, communal peace, and by forgetting differences among people. From adult education, child education, women education to newly curriculum skills development of both children and teachers, development of pedagogy skills, it depends based on primary educational role and teacher training. It builds a true global village by the establishment of meaningful primary education for the wellbeing of humankind. An initiative of Primary Education in Developing Countries is a series of articles under International development. It is also the purpose of focusing on child development from their beginning through primary education and teacher's development through appropriate training, such as teacher's professional development, workshops etc. The outcome of the article is aware of human development through education through training and development. The methodology of this article is through books, academic journals, making drafts, then its final draft through the understanding of sources. Feature question is; what do we finally achieve from our efforts for the launching of a flexible and successful primary educational module worldwide for children, women and adults?

Keywords:

Universal Education, Pedagogy Skill Development, Student/Teachers Skill Development, Human Productivity, Modern Attitude, Canada's Contribution, UNESCO, Bilingualism and Learning Talk by Talking as a Modern Way of Education by the Harvard Graduate School of Education and Dr. Catherine Snow, Play Work of Leeds University, England and the Play Leadership a New Approach of Early Childhood, Educational Model of Junior Achievement of Alberta and Northern Territories (JA), Article 31 of the UNCRC, Literacy and Adult Education, Gender Equality, Women and Child Education.

Introduction

Education is the weapon of human development, if we can start from the beginning that would be great, therefore initiative of the development of primary education which relates from our childhood in the name of early childhood education or primary education needs to be updated through universal education launched by the United Nations and its modernization of lesson plan, technically we called modern attitude. There's a global standard of education through which developing countries can be developed if they follow by launching in their educational institutes, changing their educational plan and come out from a traditional European lesson to a life skill development lesson plan. Newly curriculum of educational plan can give this award of every child, women and adults of developing countries, and in developed countries as well. Newly Curriculum lesson plan designed by teachers professional development through pedagogical skills, their development by economic reward, recognition and thus it can reflects on student education as well to accepting a good quality education for the changes of their social-economic circumstances as well as changes of economic order of the countries and thus to be equally co-operative with developed countries to create a beautiful educated world where no war, communalities exists. It is a dream still but it can be a reality through the establishment of quality education and to educate into this system. True education can give us everything that we expect in our subconscious mind.

Literature Review:

Primary Education in developed countries through early education, junior high and high school are made by world standard which should be followed by the developing world through modernization of its educational curriculum and to come out from a traditional European style made by social studies, math, and numeracy studies. It is about human development, therefore under new curriculum daily life skills are important in the lesson for training which can change entire developing countries from poor to rich. Unfortunately, it has not reached its height that has been expected. It is due to lack of intention by the government of developing countries, it is due to social-religious-economic problems in those countries, therefore whatever UN tried to set up a global model of education through its free universal education has been succeed that is expected, it has not given equal importance on various things such as quality education, classroom attendance, professional development, financial reward and it has not got equal success from all the developing countries, therefore success has been divided based on country's economic structure such as lower-income countries, middle-income countries, high-income countries. Without economic stability or a sound financial budget on education, it is hard to get success in primary education.

Methodology:

I write my essay through an extensive search of online resources, journals, and books. It is a combination of books, journals, and online resources like websites. I think about the entire article and build my ideas after the collection of resources from links. I write my ideas in the introduction, conclusion and many areas as my thought, my understanding. I make a draft essay and then from that writing I write my final essay. Most of my essays are on general writing instead of formula, statistics-based, because of my likeness on a general expression which is easy to understand for everyone. I write in my words for my understanding finally and as my exploration, therefore I write that I think, I may be right or wrong but in social science, everyone has the right to write just like the right to education.

Result and Discussion:

Education is the cornerstone of the social-economic- cultural-spiritual development of every country in the world. It is a way that institutes, societies and communities can increase their productivity and thus improves every day. Because of educational effects over society, poverty can be reduced; it is knowledge, a hope for a human being. It is a weapon in developing countries through which poverty, social crime can be reduced or full stop. Due to various terms such as globalization, neoliberalism and so on the economy has been transformed by technology world-wide and to operate this economy well

trained and intellectually flexible minded people, the labour force is needed. Education thus becomes important for everyone. Education is only an option that can create various paths or options for people to survive if laid off by the company or other organizations; it is because of securing various jobs by the people. Primary education is a pathway for every human being from their childhood, as a base that can produce literate and numerate people to solve problems everywhere, whether workplace or home. Primary education in developed countries begins through daycare, elementary school and they have various forms of development of children such as art education, education by crafts, providing healthy snacks, which creates a meaningful relationship with nutrition as well. Unfortunately, most developing countries are not equipped with these forms of primary education; their national curriculum has no core skill contained education which is the base of children's development. Girls are not allowed to go school or they have been discriminated by the school board in various developing countries, this is something controversial primary education and effects to build a base of human capital for development. This is unfortunate. However, to fulfill those shortcomings education must be spread within children's, more children's in the school to learn basic core skills and thus be master the curriculum and complete primary education. Access to the school is very important for every student, students are going to school but have no learning of education is meaningless for development. Developing countries must focus on these problems; they should increase the education budget and basically in primary education. Relocation funds are one of the ways of solution which is possible in middle-income countries, but for low-income countries, it is difficult because of financial instability. Economic crisis is a factor that effects in developing countries educational standard, which is going down day by day, as a result, competition in education, social innovation, discovery, economic standard has increased between countries, low income developing countries are getting down, they are not able to produce a talent communities, individual, their national scientific inventions and thus losing ways to be developed or at least compete with other middle income developing countries, which creates a large population of poverty. Adaptation of advance knowledge is the key to the future development of every country, especially developing countries for advancement; therefore communication, literacy, problem-solving skill, training and education of labor force are necessary to increase and to add as primary educational criteria for a solid foundation. Education has vast role for the economic, social and spiritual development, that can amalgamate economic, social and spiritual advancement of communities, societies and individual by higher earnings, higher productivity, better health, and sophisticated manners and attitudes, through educational activities such as teaching, learning, and so on, national integrity, ideology, philosophical thought can increase and it has increased by world- renowned scholars of various countries. Primary education has a tremendous role in countries' economic development. Developed countries have given importance on primary school enrollment and as a result, they have sufficient educated labor force for their economic growth, therefore it is clear that primary education and gross national product are related each other for countries economic development because of educated skilled labor as they are knowledgeable and sensitive about just in time and productivity. Without attaining primary education, it was not possible to be developed for 110 developed and developing countries of the late nineteenth and early twentieth century's. Primary education had a positive effect over 110 developed and developing countries, among them, twenty-two East Asian and Latin American countries were economically developed by the effectiveness of primary education, while fifty-four East Asian, Latin American, African and Middle Eastern countries were economically developed by the positive effects of secondary education. Universal primary enrollment was wonderfully useful in Hong Kong, South Korea, Israel, Japan, Singapore, it was not only primary but secondary education as well. It has been observed that their labour force was literate and followed the system of universal primary and secondary education just before to achieve massive economic development. Effectiveness of primary and secondary education increases earnings and productivity, it has been realized that the rate of social return was 15 to 17 percent for secondary, while 27 percent was for secondary education. It has also been realized that the effectiveness of earnings influenced productivity as well, and it was possible due to knowledgeable labor force on their physical productivity, this is evidence that how they are related to each other, that I mentioned before. Data said that four years of primary education

increased the productivity of farmers 8.7 percent, while 10 percent in the countries undergoing modernization mostly in Asia. Primary education increases social development such as improvement of child health and nutrition which has been possible through women education because of its close relations with child health, it has been observed that children of educated mother live healthier and longer and due to educational knowledge mother of the children can decide about her child's nutrition, preference for foods and its proper distribution in the household. Social development through education increases modern attitude through thinking of rationality, empirical, egalitarian values that are important for the development of social and political institutes. Higher thinking and believes spreads by the terms of global development, global institutional citizenship. Although modern attitudes were initially believed to be transmitted through the formal structure of schools, the influence of curriculum seems to be more direct within children, and it was the result of a new school curriculum made by modern attitude. Primary education has important role on cognitive development, such as more effectiveness through the modern attitude (newly curriculum) on reading, writing, numeracy, problem-solving and thus increases more human productivity from their childhood, it is an example of social development through the innovative development of child minding who are countries future, therefore it has been suggested that for more social cognitive development developing countries must teach school-age children the skills targeted by the primary education which would be useful for their earnings and productivity and thus make a country rich and developed by economically and socially. So, the cognitive skill development by the primary education through modern attitude, I mean through newly school curriculum is important in every country to build their base and thus be forward for the development of their spiritual, social, economic, cultural and citizen's identity. However, unfortunately, educational misbalance between developed and developing countries are growing tremendously, rate of immigration increases from developing to developed countries for primary studies, secondary studies, higher studies because of its much better cognitive development skill (reading, writing, problem-solving, numerical etc. following an updated school curriculum as modern attitude). Simply, developed countries are investing more finance for the cognitive skill development of their children while developing countries are unable to do it because of insufficient economic condition if we discuss on African countries like Sudan, Algeria, Congo, Asian countries like North Korea, Nepal, it is understandable, cognitive development skills of the citizens of lower-income countries are not meeting the standard of international criteria (under education). Example shows that fewer than 60 percent of the children who enter in the low-income countries and about 70 percent of the children who enter school in the lower-middle-income countries reach the last year of primary school (the official primary school cycle in most countries spans six years for students to meet curriculum objectives such as meeting basic literacy and numeracy skill, ability to apply basic skills into problems) but they are not able to complete primary education because of many reasons such as financial obligations, blind faith, prejudice against communities, untouchability etc. as a result only 30 percent of the adults in the labor force has completed primary school in those poorest countries. Economy of the developing countries are growing rapidly, Indian government launched various scheme for the development of India such as shining India, make in India, but the problems are related from their roots because of lacking international standard of education which is designed by modern attitude, in India curriculums are traditional, no intention to follow universal education and to transfer into modern attitude curriculum, as a result, a low percentage of youth completes their primary education and even they complete but do not qualify to meet the standard. Qualified and educated skilled labor are must for the development of countries infrastructure, using technology to agriculture and industrial production, but unfortunately, the fraction of adult in developing countries who are educated enough to adapt and apply modern technology is perilously low. This problem we can describe as a lack of human capital, therefore billion people of India do not recognize as their property but an explosion of the population who are less productive to fill-out their demand in daily life. Resolution of the problem is to launched new curriculum in primary education, increasing the number of primary school emphasis on learning and reading, primary education is important due to student's basic level, they learn through primary education from the beginning, it is their base to learning basic attitudes, approaches of various quality, it is a pre-requisite for the development of

human resources which is required to change technological demands for the twenty-first century. It is something that needs to be shared by modern technology to a large number of people to participate in the process of economic transformation, it requires for the balance of the globalized world, otherwise, a poor system of education will damage the entire system of human capital development and as a result, the development of entire country will go down and thus it will become an isolated and bankrupt nation. There are three phases of primary education in developing countries that is expanded availability, search for relevance and economic seriousness. No doubt those developing countries are doing their best for the expansion of their primary schooling system to provide universal access to schooling their children and youth, example shows that between 1965 to 1985 student enrollment in primary schooling has been increased from 298 million to 482 million in developing countries. In the late 1960's countries from the world starts criticism about the traditional schooling system which is expensive and unproductive for the people, then its relevant search of alternative starts such as modern attitude equipped by cognitive development, skill development, various innovative process and the learning of attitude but traditional primary schooling system remain today in most of the developing countries. One of the most comprehensive crisis of primary education in developing countries is low capacity, it was not mass education but for few elites within a class-based structure and it indicated a feudal system of their primary education. Finally, an approach of mass education has been set up by the effort of the United Nations under its Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948; it declared a universal system of education which is for everyone, free education in the primary structure and the requirement of elementary school as mandatory. The benefit of the education is clear that is development of the country technologically, financially, intellectually, culturally, environmentally, mentally, physically, spiritually, socially and academically, developed countries understood way before then developing countries that educated worker can change and this is why from the beginning of their country role they gave importance on education and its roots primary education. UNESCO started the expansionist model of education in various ways like regional meetings around the world, in 1956 and 1963 Lima (Peru) and Santiago (Chile) was the host for the regional meeting of Latin American and Caribbean free and compulsory primary education. Asian countries met in Karachi (Pakistan) and Tokyo (Japan) for the incensement of ratio from 70 % (1964) to 90 % (1980), Addis Ababa was a host for primary educational initiatives in the African region. Their aim was unique that is the development of primary education through increasing student enrollment and it has succeeded as well. In Africa student's enrollment to primary school increased from approximately 30 million (1970) to approximately 60 million, in Asia, it was from 243 million (1970) to 330 (1980) and in Latin America and the Caribbean was approximately 47 million (1970) to approximately 65 million (1980). Result of free enrollment came thus and fantastically, expensive education is a problem in Asia, Latin and the Caribbean and Africa because of poverty and due to feudal system in society, feudal way established through the enrollment of elite class but this was not the solution of countries development as whole, elite society go to school for their individual development but mass education through free education is for universal development, countries development, otherwise terms of globalization, economic socialization, maintaining living standard have no value and it cannot be controlled by the elite but spread within common people as well in the name of mass education. So, the year of 1960, 1970 and beyond were the decades of exceptional expansion of primary school capacity, it was 5.2 in low-income countries, 4.1 in lower-middle-income countries and 3.4 in upper- middle-income countries, total number of school doubled and teachers were tripled in developing countries as the theme of universal education launched by the UN. But it was not the same picture in the '80s, enrollment was declined because of financial instability late '70s and '80s in developing countries and slackness of the entire process. According to UNESCO and World Bank, approximately 145 million children age six to eleven in developing countries did not attend school in 1985, 90 percent of the children were from low and lower-middle-income countries and 60 percent were girls among them. So, it was hope in few years and not hope in few years because of economic situation each year, slackness of process, and the declining of the national budget in education, however, the consciousness of relevant and better delivery education was increased on the other side as well. Some countries like Pakistan, Kenya, The Philippines, Trinidad

&Tobago publicized reviews of their educational objectives and policies through which they were trying to build a completely fresh and new educational approach structured by a universal curriculum that meets international standards. President Julius Nyerere of Tanzania's statement about the education of self-reliance was approachable where he was trying to adapt an education that can impact on-farm production and Tanzania's need through farming and be more effective. Therefore, several developing countries gave importance on newly curriculum, a country like Malaysia established a large curriculum development center, initiatives on teachers training programs and institutions in Sierra Leone; Liberia by UN was a unique example of the revolution of primary education. Malaysia, El-Salvador launched an educational television program. Nicaragua used radio to teach mathematics, Ethiopia, Jamaica, and Kenya uses radio to reach student's and trained teachers, Bangladesh, Malaysia, Liberia, Indonesia, Philippines, Jamaica experimented a new method like using materials and peer group to provide primary education at a reasonable cost and through institutionalized. Youth club in Benin, a rural education center in Burkina Faso is all efforts as an alternative of limited access to a classroom education in developing countries, which was a new educational curriculum as well. However, schooling in developing countries are completely different in developed countries, if we compare, we observe that student-teacher's ratio is balanced in developed countries, students are healthy and well-fed, attend classes in a modern well-equipped building, take 900 hours of learning from teachers who are minimum 16 years of formal education holder, but on the side, this wealthy picture is completely different in developing countries, where student attend a shelter less school, curriculum is poorly designed, student-teacher ratio is highly imbalanced, teachers are ten years formal education holder and get 500 hours learning yearly from school. If we compare learning ratio then students from the developed world are getting many hours for learning and they learn more vocabulary than the students from developing countries. According to Dr. Catharine Snow of Harvard Graduate School of Education who teaches us through professional education program, Learning Talk by Taking- A Developmental Approach to Maximizing Language and Literacy Skills, that, Knowledge gap and Vocabulary gap, count in numbers such as 30 million gaps during language development either knowledge or words learning through textbook, photography, storytelling, arts, and many other sources of learning, however, it is based on family structure and its influences on children such as developed professional parents vs low-income parents, where children from developed family can learn extensive amounts of words, poor families children can't learn that much, they are always less 500-1000 words learner than rich family kid's, and it is because of parents less interaction with children, therefore talk much in meaningful way with children for knowledge and words, and to reduce gap, comprehensive reading with children is another way for language development. Her comments on gaping vocabulary and language also work between the students of developed and developing countries due to less learning hours. As per Dr. Snow, Listening is important, so listen primary kids what they want to say, care them, understand them, response their noise, facial expression, interpret, listen their question and answer, talk productive, co-operate, befriend with children (dominant and non-dominant way) love them, like them, never avoid or show negative approach such as I don't know, I don't care, oh!! etc. good for you (good for you for what? like no logical way to say this sentence, a negative sign), make a circle group(mealtime talking) in a dinner table, a perfect time to teach them social, interactive, group approach, we together, language and literacy development (literacy is good for class performance, good grade) and a polite mouth, language development, literacy development, knowledge development by parents talking at home, listening, taking care children through parents as primary sources. Pre-school setting, classroom setting, learning concept, powerful, attractive, dynamic topic brings a joy in child mind as well, so it is not only talking or reading or listening, it is something about environmental standard through setting up for the safety of kids, their recognition (they may be kids but have strong sense on their identity). The quality of the classroom needs to be more focused. Instructional quality needs to be more focused such as teacher's language, which could be complex, diverse, however, something needs to be the outcome from their teaching. The curriculum has to be meaningful and productive. we need to listen children if they have any suggestion on classroom setting (grade 4, 5 6), good Curriculum, listening, talking, questioning is relevant for child education, primary education and their

development, curriculum of grade 4 to 8 need to be weighty, engaged, question-based, and dilemmas (no answer but a classroom discussion where kids can participate for a discussion and find out their point on a topic, it is not judgmental but a freedom for every kid). According to Dr. Snow, comprehensive reading, phonological awareness (phonetic/linguistic), decoding (analyzing) are important in the 21st century's global economy. Comprehensive reading helps students to understand the meaning of their text, and then they start questions. It is our speech which is students learning, it is not something memorizing, it is teachers responsibility that students understand the relevant of the topic and provide enough background knowledge and then read the topic efficiently, background knowledge is important for the kids of grade 4 to 8 because they pronounce accurately, read word correctly and can analyze the topic(decoding skill), and make sure they know the meaning of the words that they are reading, vocabulary test and decoding test are prediction of children's outcomes from the topic they read which is reading comprehension assessment for Grade 4 to 8 students. Relevant content knowledge is another important skill that helps kids to know the meaning of the words and also understand the perspective of the situation that text was written. Trust is very important but to whom I will trust? suppose a situation, that austerity is the solution of international economic problem but other says economic expansion through reducing tax is the solution of the problem(to whom I will trust? which one is true?), in this case, analysis is important using academic language, understanding the perspective they are writing from, following their arguments and knowing enough what austerity is? And what expansionist economic policies can think about? though yet it will not be a full understanding, but I will understand their ground that in which ground they are arguing. However, phonological skill, decoding skill, comprehensive reading skill are important for grade 4 to 8 children's and it is our(teacher's) duty to set up a classroom curriculum based on that skill, therefore we also need to be well trained and complete understanding of that skill, but skills like those are not that easy for the kids, so far Dr. Snow said that talking is the best skill to solve out problem. Classroom discussion is another skill for grade 4 to 8 students, it is something allows them to create and discuss as debate, is bilingualism makes student smart? Open-ended questions. It creates togetherness, independent point of view from everyone because it has no final answer, it is a right of speech and analyzing independently searching multiple sources (are all skills). Kindergarten to grade 1 to 8 needs to encouraged, motivated, taking care, making them interesting, a safe classroom for discovering, and taking care of their content of language. This is Harvard teacher's way to show the structure of developed model of primary education and it's operation among primary kids, unfortunately, the standard of education that mentioned by Dr. Snow is not available in developing countries because of lacking materials, lacking classroom access, and many more social- economical-enthusiastic problem in developing countries and thus create a huge gap between the students of two different sides on knowledge and vocabulary which can be easily understandable during their study abroad in developed universities, they confront various challenge at the beginning and upon several years of education, interaction they finally can adapt and meet the international standard of education. So, the developing countries must follow those instructions that have been said by the professor which is the reflection of an orderly school environment, educational effectiveness, school effectiveness, academic emphasis, and instructional leadership of the teachers by cognitive skill training which teach them how to manage challenges in school and thus concentrate on student learning. It has been observed that curricular of the primary education is almost same worldwide, in primary school more than 50 percent of the time is spent teaching language skill such as math, science, social studies which are half of the total time, and one fourth on language studies and the other areas receive less attention. In developing countries primary educational curriculum gives more importance on agriculture, business and domestic science lesson in the classroom than the industrialized countries based on their agrarian economic system, furthermore textbooks are the main curricula in most developing countries, unfortunately, curriculum of the textbooks are poorly designed based on their school grade such as first-grade mathematics and reading textbooks are appropriate but difficulties start from grade third because of hard mathematics textbooks, in grade fifth mathematics textbooks are too hard while reading textbooks are too easy, which creates an imbalance text curriculum, through which students get easily frustrated. It is a result that students are not skilled or expertise on every subject, either they

are poor in mathematic or language courses because of their inability to catch the hard curriculum, it is something that too hard or too easy for students which they neither understand nor like. Textbooks are suffering from inappropriate illustrations, problems with readability, grammatical errors, deviations from the specifications set by the curriculum bureau of textbook board, lying about cultural, historical areas, hate crimes about other countries, religions etc. because of hard textbook materials teachers summarized the text reading materials for students to understand, in some developing countries textbooks were failed to reinforce the development of higher-order thinking skills such as problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Therefore, it is recommended that developing countries should improve their intended and implemented curriculum by using their primary classroom; such as modify their intended curriculum by concentration on the course taught and the number of hours officially allocated to them which is a blind alley. Instruction by the teachers and the teachers training need to be designed by innovative approaches which is scientific and attracted for the teachers and the students as well through which they can come to the classroom education, increasing teachers knowledge of the subjects matter, improving pedagogical skills, in-service training teachers education, continuous training such as professional education following the developed countries, (Harvard Graduate School of Education Department has their unique professional education through online and on-campus), distance education program, programs through electronic media and the ongoing teachers training program. In Bangladesh, an ongoing teacher training program through school-based teacher training is the success story in primary education, each teacher and assistant teachers receive two months of extensive training in general topics. Those trainings are useful to adapting the curriculum related to pupil's social and physical context to understand their learning and development, evaluating teaching and learning, managing classrooms, teacher/student relations, parent/teacher relations and community relations. It is recommended that the capacity of learning depends on the understanding of health and nutritional aspects of child and therefore these experiences must be corrected during the preschool years. Primary education is a combination of the process involving the home and school and it depends on parent's awareness and their educational background as well. It has been reported that in Philippines occupational and educational level of the parents has shaped the school attainment of their children, similar effects found in Indonesia, Brazil, and Nepal. Wealthy parents provide their children educational materials, proper nutrition, a stimulating environment, and as a result those children are a better position in classroom education than those children whose parents are not able to provide the proper home environment because of various social problems. Children need to be healthy through proper nutrition for their better achievement in education such as grade attainment, achievement test score, general intelligence, cognitive skill and concentration on the classroom; otherwise, it does not go well. However, in developing countries the background of the home environment and nutritional matters are not that good that we observe in developed countries, even it has no minimum standard as well for the children development, malnutrition is one of the biggest problems, temporary hunger is a problem as well when children do not eat breakfast. In India, China, Nepal Kenya and the Philippines malnutrition spread widely within poor children and in rural populations. In Kenya, almost 30 percent of the children are underweight, in Nepal boys are below 75 percent weight for age and only 13.5 percent of the Uttar Pradesh, India had normal height and weight for their age. The Head Start program launched by the United States of America in 1965 started for the development of the classroom especially for poor children who comes to the classroom unprepared, this program provides health, nutrition, social services for those who are in preschool program with poor situation due to health and nutrition problem, this program also trained preschool teachers for their skill readiness. Head Start program found positive for the children's development on intellectual, achievement tests, special education, class attendants, promotion, reading, writing, placement and remaining in school. Participants of the head start program especially low-income students improved a lot going through a various developmental process that has been described above. They have been succeeded in school readiness both in the US primary school and most developing countries' primary school programs. Egypt's Koranic pre-school program developed literacy during the early grades of primary school. One of the way for cognitive, social, physical, psychological,

development of pre-school and primary school children found through play work program in Scandinavian countries, The UK, New Zealand, Japan, Germany, and Romania. Play work has developed since 1940 and came from the Danish playground concept, that allowed children free play through their direction instead of play worker, freely chosen, intrinsically directed, non-goal directed, free to explore their capacity for doing things themselves in the school playground, mud play areas, large tower swings, and climbing apparatus. Play work program, a theory and practice that mechanized for redressing aspect of developmental imbalance caused by a deficit of play opportunities, found positive through the human development such as communication development, flexibility, aesthetic development, inter-relative development, increased confidence, self-esteem, motivation, curriculum enrichment, health benefit through soft and hard motor skills, development of citizenship, development of behavior which counteract anti- social activities, social inclusion of families, linkages between family, school, the wider community and through the implementation of playful pedagogy in a standard-driven society like mostly developed countries pre-school and primary school program. Article 31 of the UNCRC ensures the development of the pre-school and primary school children and declares that; children have the right to play, every child needs time and space to play, adult (play worker) should let children play, children should be able to play freely in their local areas and their school playground, children value and benefit from staffed play provision, children's play is enriched by skilled play workers(University of Leeds, The UK undergraduate and graduate play work degree), children's need extra support to enjoy their right to play. Play work should be added in the new curriculum of all developing countries as well for the development of the kids which escapes them from deprivation of all kinds and gives the right of freedom through which they can choose their way to be famous. Teaching quality and teaching time are important for student's achievements and it depends on the teachers that how they manage the classroom meaningfully. Teachers training are important but in many developing countries teachers lacks many pedagogical skills, motivation and professional commitment to teaching, are barriers for the development of primary education and pre-school educational setting. It has been observed that teaching was a regarded profession in the past, for example in Korea teachers are regarded just like king but at present teachers are not valued, especially primary school teachers, as a result, teaching profession does not encourage present youth, or they choose either secondary or high school teaching profession because of more benefit than primary teaching profession. It effects on child development through primary school education. The decline in the academic preparation of prospective teacher's effects on intellectual and academic skills that they need in their training as well as child development. However, providing general education through stipend program, pedagogical skills development, development of subject proficiency, competent teachers training program, much educational background at least the qualification of secondary education for primary school teachers, sound knowledge of the curriculum and the ability to transfer it to their students, development of critical analysis and its appraisal or evaluation, development of practice teaching under the supervision of senior and experienced teacher, more motivational approaches such as more benefit, recognition, rewarding, encouragement of professionalism, development of working condition, increases of teachers presence in school, retention of primary teachers through various professional developments program, modest salary, are few approaches that can develop primary education. It has been observed that in developed world, teachers from primary to secondary to high school has various professional program through a central board such as Edmonton Public School board or Edmonton Catholic School board in Alberta, Canada, modest salary, good pension plan, a good amount of resting time, and has fair vacations, as a result, students from the first world countries are in most advantage stage than any developing countries because of modified teachers training program frequency, teachers personal satisfaction, but in Asia, Africa or in most developing countries, teachers are theoretically respected but are poor economically, professionally and it affects negatively over students. For the betterment of primary education, the developed world has given importance on institutional and managerial strengthening and it shows how achievement of students does and the quality of teachers can be improved and increased, that is their inputs. It has been observed that both in developed and developing countries educational institutes are influenced by several associations such as parents

association, bureaucratic, social, and political context, teachers unions, local school board etc. and somehow because of influential situation, education system did not get its real fundamental principles through which improvement of students and teachers can be faster, in Venezuela education system is highly centralized and directed by the ministry of education, a hierarchical standard of power, therefore it has long process to pass or approved any good thing, teachers are depends over the ministry of education for any excuse for the educational standard, and it is quite understandable that it can or can't be approved. On the other side in Colombia, the educational system is decentralized and often ignored a notice from the central organization. Therefore we observe here that centralization and decentralization of education both have a problem because of misusing power not much think about educational improvements. Educational managers gain managerial skills throughout the system but some cannot. In developing countries, managerial and administration quality is very weak in their educational system and it is because of insufficient training, poor information system, and personal dissatisfaction. Those are inputs for human development which is unfortunately invisible in underdeveloped countries. Only solution for a strong educational system, administration is to provide freedom to managers, administrators, sufficient training, strong information system such as achievement testing, research initiatives, monitoring of information, etc. encouraging local organizations such as educational club NGO's, school funding, immediate assistance such as technical assistance, staff development, and resource development etc. which can reduce socio-political-bureaucratic red tape and improve educational development every part of the world. In Malaysia National Institute of Educational Management is an educational organization establishes by the government for staff development through planning, implementation and management skills training, quality of education can be assessed by learning measurement(student learning) which is the development of pedagogy skill, certification and selection examination, and sample-based assessment(periodic assessment test to all students for the measurement of their improvement of educational quality which has been accepted in China, two provinces in Brazil, Republic of Korea). Educational resource is another important factor for the development of education whether primary or secondary but again problems occurs in developing countries, it is also understandable that countries have their native language and because of insufficient educational skill such as interpretation, most of them have very few resources of education, because resources are widely available in English language and at the end, it has been observed that books in developing countries have insufficient information on topics or subjects which has been interpreted from original English information either in a wrong way or not fully. Lack of resources also depends on government financial budget on education and developing countries are suffering through government educational budget, India is interested on defense budget than education because of imaginary thinking that proper education for 1.25 billion people is impossible. If we analyze deeply then family planning is also not effective in India and it is because of insufficient education within the mass. Neediest people do not get the benefit of education subsidies because of their lack of knowledge, perhaps they even do not have any idea about benefit subsidy, and as a result, people from the middle class and upper-middle-class are taking this opportunity and it has various corruption within the government in most developing countries. Solution of those problems is to find out cost-effective inputs, giving importance on people welfare development through education, increasing budget on education, interpretation skill training, appropriate interpretation from English to their native language, raising tax, fundraising, improving cost-sharing, strengthening of local school finance, equal distribution of equity(make sure federal government funds goes to the local school, neediest people, poor communities and equally distributed) etc. Yugoslavia is a great example of the national committee of equity in education, in 1974 they created a self-governed education interested communities who provided fund about 85% of the cost of elementary education in entire Yugoslavia. Citizens of these education interested communities received tax funds from the government to govern the schools. We always discuss neo-liberalization, globalization, in this context everyone must help developing countries through aid, and international aid also has a big contribution to the development of primary education. Within 1981-86, 16 percent of aid went to secondary education, 17 percent in technical education, 34 percent in tertiary education and 33 percent in primary education in Sub-Saharan African from the rest of the world.

International education aid distributed mostly in Europe, North Africa and Middle East countries primary education where per students received \$1.34. Approximately 19 percent of all aid was devoted to pedagogical inputs such as teachers and textbooks, however, it was not sufficient because of donors negligence on primary education, they somehow wanted something to return of their donation and therefore they would like to invest in something that has standard and risk-free, primary educational system in developing countries has been described and it did not meet standard, however, it is also understandable that a sustained primary education is required every part of the world for the expectation of international aid from other countries, therefore development of primary education must require. The demands of primary education rise everywhere in the world, it is a human rights, and a way to achieve sustainable development outcomes, education is a weapon through which children and youth learn various skills to solve their problems they face every day in their life, it is a key to reducing poverty, achieving gender equality, equity, man and woman rights, child rights, and achieve social development, woman education is important for their strength because we know that woman in developing countries are ignored and isolated from the mainstream of lifeline, they use for sexual product and household activities, community education is important as well, it is a hope, stability, and structure for the future of human being, it helps children and youth to come out from trauma caused by war, disaster and community conflict, therefore in Syria, Palestine, Yemen, educational activities provided by several nonprofit organizations must require for the development of postwar citizens. Canada as a developed and human rights country is helping worldwide, it's development assistance focuses on establishing a strong education system worldwide especially in developing countries, Canada helped to build the capacity of government

education officials, helped to support new and returning teacher training programs, institutes, helped to improve the development and the distribution of relevant, gender-sensitive learning materials and its curriculum, supported to make school responsive to girls water, sanitation and hygiene needs, working to end of school violence, harmful practices, provided support to meet the education needs of crisis-affected children, Canada supported key multicultural organizations, such as the Global Partnership for Education, and the UNESCO Institute for statistics. Not only in basic education, Canada also helped by financial assistance for the assurance of women education, adult education and the youth education, that they have sufficient knowledge, skill and competencies which is required for their employment and to the contribution of economic growth, literacy training, vocational training, numeracy training were part of Canada's assistance program in the developing countries especially for those who did not have basic education, also supported funds for the international scholarship for the support of students and professionals in developing countries and to reduce the poverty, those scholarship helps to create innovation leaders for next generation for the developing countries who can properly lead their country. Primary education is a must for everyone according to UNICEF because education is the only way of weapons that can teach children to reduce poverty, increase socialization within the community, and prevent diseases including HIV/AIDS and malaria. Universal education is important to keep students in secondary education and a new basic education after primary education because of its low portfolio. Universal education is free offered by UNESCO but females are mostly affected yet a modern, free education in developing countries because of social, religious deep-rooted cultural beliefs., not only that, in developing countries even public school is not free, cost of books, uniforms and teachers are borne by the students families, approximately 67million children in entire developing countries are denied by the right to education, approximately 115 million children in primary school age are not enrolled in school,

approximately 226 million children do not attend secondary school, illiteracy is the highest among females, it is about more than 70% in 20 developing countries, girls are less likely to be in school, while boys are to repeat grades or drop-out, in the African continent less than 50% literacy among children ages 18 and under while youth literacy in South American and European countries are 90-100%. Therefore free universal education as a modern attitude of education which can meet the standard of international education does not work still in developing countries and the reasons are

above that I discussed. Developing countries still adopt a traditional western model with an emphasis of math, science, language, and social studies, and the topics are like Greek mythology, tectonic movement, prime numbers etc. which has been taught from centuries, nothing is new which can generate children about their lifestyle, about the way for their future, in Canada, there's an organization, called Junior Achievement of Canada(JA) and they are provincially divided, in Alberta Junior Achievement of Alberta and Northern Territories has a unique style of educational curriculum through which we as volunteers teach kindergarten kids for their future ambition, what they want to be and how, it is a combination of science, business and arts, which I can say an example of modern attitude, I mean a new curriculum of primary education. However, few developing countries in the world achieved a new milestone because of their new think-tank, Ethiopia got a great achievement by applying an education sector plan through which countries girls enrollment in primary education has increased from 40% in 1999 to 90% in 2008, Burkina Faso also got a modest achievement in girl education, 73% girls enrolled in primary education and continuing their secondary education. BRAC, a most successful nonprofit organization in Bangladesh owns over 32,000 primary schools, Pratham, a nonprofit organization in India provides literacy and other educational supports among 33 million children and Escuela Nuevo, the Colombian program of mono and multi- grade teaching that has grown to 20,000 school in Colombia and develops a classroom materials, pedagogical approaches in which students can learn

in self-directed environment. UNESCO's school for life is a new model of modern attitude for the development of primary education which combined traditional studies and the new model of financial, health and administrative skills among students and teachers, the model of school for life is inspired by adult education that is self-efficacy as a critical foundation of positive livelihood in developing countries and its active learning pedagogies. Steps have been taken by several NGO's such as BRAC, Pratham, Escuela Nuevo, youth club in Benin, rural education center in Burkina Faso, governmental organization in Malaysia and efforts by UNESCO etc. but has it developed, human development, literacy by primary education has been improved by efforts but I do not think that it has developed and sufficient for the developing world, it is due to intentionally by the government of many third world countries, it is due to socio-economic-deep spiritual belief and many more. The report mentions that illiteracy has increased in developing countries, adult education has no value due to surrounding circumstances, approximately 175 million young people have no basic literacy skill, approximately 250 million children are not learning basic reading, and math skills, and approximately 774 million were adult illiterate(2011). Unfortunately, India, China, Bangladesh, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Egypt, Brazil, Indonesia and Congo are countries where three- quarters of world's illiterate adults live and as I said before that women and children are the most victims of illiteracy, as a positive approach attendance of primary school has increased in developing countries by several donations from developed countries, UN's several welfare programs, and through many more efforts but on the other side illiteracy and adult education have been neglected, I mean there is no complete model of universal education where all educational sectors have been fulfilled or have given equal importance. However efforts like World Education Forum summit in Dakar, Senegal (2000) agreed on six global goals such as expanding and improving on child care development and early education, giving importance on child, women, minorities for their complete access of free primary education and literacy,

learning needs of all young and adults are met, achievement of 50% adult literacy worldwide by 2015, and the incensement, improvement of continuing education, elimination of gender discrimination and establishment of gender equality, and making sure that girls can access of quality education (educational quality depends on three things; efficiency, relevance and something more) and have equal status with boys for the access of good quality education, establishment and improvement of quality education so that citizens can achieve educational excellence and proper training on quality education such as literacy, numeracy and necessary life skills through basic education. Make sure that marginalization and poverty are decreased, enough financial budget for primary education by the government of the developing countries, proper campaigning of the right to education and child play,

creation of an equal status between boys and girls for the development of primary education in developing countries, including developed countries because there's a gap between rich and poor family children in developed countries as well, as a result, the requirements of vocabulary vary between poor and rich kids which affects their basic educational quality. We should remind that women's education increased employable skills within women and they invest their money mostly for their household than man, therefore an educated world is healthier and more humane based on an equal standard between men and women.

Conclusion:-

The article is about problems of primary education and its supportive ways in the developing world, developed world as well. We have taken initiatives by the UN declaration of human rights about the right to education, free universal education as the mandatory requirements to every human worldwide and many more efforts. What do we finally achieve from our efforts for the launching of a flexible and successful primary educational module worldwide for children, women and adults? This is my research question. I would say through my written

observation that we did not reach that height we should, globalization, neo-liberalization, post-modernism and many theories, ideologies have been set-up for the global development, I mean its economic development, educational development, and to build the world as one and united village, we say global village. It is somehow successful if I think economically through liberalization of trade policies, tariffs, academic exchanges between north and south countries but the main focus here is primary education in developing countries and somehow in developed countries as well. Differences between haves and have-nots are increasing in developing countries if a true educational module like a free universal education launches worldwide, why then poverty increases, why identical values are increasing, why economic, social, and political differences are increasing among developing countries in the name of lower-income, middle income, high income developing countries? Because differences still exist between the developed and developing world and it is because of misunderstanding between two cultures, educational curriculums and social-religious, spiritual beliefs and economical differences, it can't be solved because of racial prospects as well, the educational prospect can reunite Germany, but can't Korea or Greater India, why? The answer will be given by the future generation upon an evolutionary observation of world culture, social and economic differences. So the solution is depending on the total elimination of racial issues between communities, between countries, it will truly be a united global village with meaningful access to flexible qualified primary education when racial issues will be wiped out. True Institutional or Global Citizenship can be established in a meaningful world where war, identity, race, discrimination, deep faith will vanish and thus a good module of primary education can be set up among all kinds of citizens. This is the present demand of the entire human being.

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